

Improve your findability

Ensuring potential users can easily find your resource is key to expanding your user base. Here are some tips to begin with:

By Search Engines

To enhance your Search Engine Optimisation (SEO), start by analyzing the keywords that lead visitors to your website. To achieve this, go to “Acquisition > Search Engines & Keywords” in [SIB Matomo](#). For instance, if your resource is mostly discovered by its name rather than through search queries related to scientific topics, it indicates that:

- Your resource has a **strong brand recognition**.
- Most of your users are existing ones, suggesting an opportunity to **attract new users**. Consult the factsheet dedicated to «**Attracting attention to your resource**» to gain visibility towards potential users.

Below you will find a set of **basic rules for SEO**. They are not intended to be exhaustive and apply first to Google. Conduct a self-assessment and follow these SEO recommendations to **improve your search engine visibility**.

→ Check your code

- Ensure **markup validity** with the [W3C validator](#) and **code brevity** (15% of tags, max)
- Serve your site in **HTTPS**
- Have a **short domain name**
- Embed valid **schema.org metadata** in the **JSON-LD format** in the head element (check with [Schema validator](#)).
- Use **semantic HTML elements** such as `<h1>` or `<table>` instead of `` or `<div>` for a clearer meaning for browsers and developers. Especially when using header tags, use them in order *h1, h2, h3, ...*. Do not skip tags.
- Add **alt properties** to image and link tags
- Provide a **sitemap**.
- Regularly check that **links are not broken** (using SEO tool suites or XENU Link Sleuth, for example)

→ Check your design

- Implement **responsive design**
- Add the **Resource logo at the top left** of each page as a link to the homepage
- Add a **search field**
- Use a **personalized 404 error** page with key links like home, about, etc.
- Add **breadcrumbs** on top of pages to clarify navigation for both search engines and users

Pay attention to how you gain new users

Identifying the main channels that drive new visitors to your website — such as search engines, direct access, or referrals — can help you boost your traffic. To evaluate this, check the “Acquisition > Overview” section in SIB Matomo.

→ Check performance/speed

The time Google spends crawling your website is limited. If loading/rendering your pages takes too much time, the indexing might be impaired.

- Check your website performance with [SIB Matomo](#), [GTmetrix](#), and/or [PageSpeed Insights](#).
- Use **minified** JS and CSS files
- No slideshow, Google map, etc. or **other long to load/render elements** on the homepage
- Use [Server-Side Rendering \(SSR\)](#) over Single-Page Applications (SPAs) built with React

→ Define keywords

Help Google understand page content by including a definition of search query terms in your pages.

To select keywords, you can use [Google Trends](#), the [AdWord keyword planner](#), [Ubersuggest](#), or [ChatGPT](#) - there are plenty of prompt examples online. Then use these keywords or terms with equivalent meaning:

- in the **URL** (domain name + sub-domains),
- in the **page title**,
- in the **top menu**,
- in the **<h1> tag** and in the **<h2> tags** (in this order),
- in the **text**.

In Registries

→ All resources

Should be listed in (provided they meet the criteria):

- [Expasy.org](#), the Swiss Bioinformatics Resource Portal
- [ELIXIR's bio.tools](#) and their training materials in [TeSS](#) and [SIB's Glittr.org](#)
- [SciCrunch](#) (includes ontologies)

→ Databases

Should have an entry in:

- [Wikipedia](#) as well as in existing gene or protein pages with information from your resources and/or with links to corresponding entry in resources. Seek advice with the **Communications team** as there are specific rules to get published on Wikipedia (without having a "conflict of interest" banner)
- [NAR Database Summary Paper Alphabetic List](#) (requires a publication in the NAR Database Issue)
- [NAR db status](#) (requires a publication in the NAR Database Issue)
- [Bioregistry.io](#) (includes ontologies)
- [FAIRsharing](#) (includes ontologies) which is included in the Japanese Integbio Database Catalog
- [Database Commons](#), a catalog of worldwide biological databases in China
- [re3data](#), the registry of research data repositories
- [YummyData](#) and [Linked Open Data Cloud](#) (for SPARQL endpoints)

→ Ontologies

Should be included in:

- The National Center for Biomedical Ontology [BioPortal](#), or its derivatives such as [Agroportal](#) for agriculture and [Ecoportal](#) for ecology and related domains.
- The [EMBL-EBI Ontology Lookup Service](#)
- [Ontobee](#), the default linked data server for most [OBO Foundry](#) library ontologies

→ Software tools

Should consider:

- Making their code public on [GitHub](#)
- Packaging their code and environment using [Conda](#) (Conda and standard Python packages)
- Publishing Python packages in [PyPi](#)
- Sharing your open-source software in [Bioconductor](#)
- Distributing container images in [Docker hub](#) and/or [Quay Container Registry](#)
- Listing their packages (e.g conda), containers (e.g docker, singularity) and workflows in [BioContainers](#)

→ Datasets

Should be deposited in [Zenodo](#) to obtain a DOI and record their **metadata**.

Your contacts:

[Communications team](#)
[Biodata Resources team](#)

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